

Impact of Social Media in Technological World

D. Santhiya, W. Jeba Grace, S. Nandhini

Sri Krishna Adithya College of Arts and Science, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India

ABSTRACT

Social media is a platform for people to discuss their issues and opinions. Before knowing the aspects of social media people must have to know what is social media? Social media are computer tools that allows people to share or exchange information's, ideas, images, videos and even more with each other through a particular network. In this paper we cover all aspects of social media with its positive and negative effect. it is projected that the future social media technology will increasingly result from virtually endless interactions of company/company generated content and user/user generated content. Competition and information clutter is also projected to increase substantially in the future. Therefore the companies will have to tap into the lucrative social media platforms in order to actively market to target consumers. This paper gives a brief definition of what media is and what are the effects of media on society. During the course of this literature various types of Impacts of media on the individual, his family and society are highlighted.

How to cite this paper: D. Santhiya | W. Jeba Grace | S. Nandhini "Impact of Social Media in Technological World" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-4 | Issue-2, February 2020, pp.1013-1015, URL: www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd30233.pdf

Copyright © 2019 by author(s) and International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development Journal. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)

1. INTRODUCTION

Human beings express their nature by creating and recreating an organization which guides and controls their behaviour in many ways. This organization liberates and limits the activities of men, sets up standards for them to follow and maintain. Whatever the imperfections and tyrannies it has exhibited in human history, it is necessary condition of fulfillment of life. This organization which is responsible for fulfillment of life of every individual is called society. Man in every society has suffered from one or the other problems. Men in modern societies are also experiencing various problems and his behavior gets affected by many things, media is one of them.: Media is the plural of the word medium. Media are the vehicles or channels which are used to convey information, entertainment, news, education, or promotional messages are disseminated. Media includes every broadcasting and narrowcasting medium such as television, radio, newspapers, billboards, mails, telephone, fax, internet etc (the main means of mass communication). The mass media occupy a high proportion of our leisure time: people spend, on average, 25 hours per week watching television, and they also find time for radio, cinema, magazines and newspapers. For children, watching television takes up a similar amount of time to that spent at school or with family and friends although the term social media has taken on numerous meanings and is somewhat open to interpretation as the domain is constantly reinventing itself, generally the term refers to "websites and applications used for social networking" (Oxford Dictionaries 2012). Given that definition, one would wonder what the term "social networking" really means. Social media encompasses social

networks, as well as content oriented networks. These sites have become a day to day routine for the people. Social media has been mainly defined to refer to "the many relatively inexpensive and widely accessible electronic tools that facilitate anyone to publish and access information, collaborate on a common effort, or build relationship"

2. IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON VARIOUS FIELDS:

Impact of Social Media on Education As per the survey of previous research, 90% of college students use social networks. Technology has shown a rapid development by introducing small communication devices and we can use these small communication devices for accessing social

networks any time anywhere, as these gadgets include pocket computers, laptops, iPads and even simple mobile phones (which support internet) etc. The possibility of media effects is often seen to challenge individual respect and autonomy, as if a pro-effects view presumes the public to be a gullible mass, cultural dopes, vulnerable to an ideological hypodermic needle, and as if television was being proposed as the sole cause of a range of social behaviours. Such a stereotyped view of research tends to pose an equally stereotyped alternative view of creative and informed viewers making rational choices about what to see. Overview articles often describe a history of progress over the past seventy years of research which alternates between these two extremes -- first we believed in powerful effects, then came the argument for null effects, then the return to strong effects etc. -- a history whose contradictions become apparent when old research is reread with new eyes.

3. SOCIOLOGICAL THEORIES OF COMMUNICATION:

The sociological approach to communication theory is based on assumption that there exists a definite relationship between mass communication and social change. Some of the relevant theories which are going to be discussed here are The cultivation theory: It was developed by George Gerbner in 1967. It is based on the assumption that mass media have subtle effects on audiences who unknowingly absorb the dominant symbols, images, and messages of media. He calls it "cultivation of dominant image pattern". According to this theory a long persistent exposure to TV is capable of cultivating common beliefs about the world. Social Learning Theory: It is one of the most widely used theories in mass communication. According to this theory the media are active but subtle educators in teaching readers, viewers, listeners about the world. An important component of this theory is that it explains how people can learn from observations alone.

4. POSITIVE EFFECTS OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON EDUCATION:

- Social media gives a way to the students to effectively reach each other in regards to class ventures, bunch assignments or for help on homework assignments.
- Many of the students who do not take an interest consistently in class might feel that they can express their thoughts easily on social media.
- Teachers may post on social media about class activities, school events, homework assignments which will be very useful to them.

- It is seen that social media marketing has been emerging in career option. Social media marketing prepares young workers to become successful marketers.
- The access of social media provides the opportunity for educators to teach good digital citizenship and the use of Internet for productivity

5. NEGATIVE EFFECTS OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON EDUCATION:

- The first concern about the negative effect comes to mind is the kind of distraction to the students present in the class. As teachers were not able to recognize who is paying attention in the classroom.
- One of the biggest breakdown of social media in education is the privacy issues like posting personal information on online sites.
- In some of the scenario there were many in appropriate information posted which may lead the students to the wrong side.
- Because of social media students lose their ability to engage themselves for face to face communication.
- Many of the bloggers and writers posts wrong information on social sites which leads the education system to failure.

What type of media is used by youth • Computers • Texting • Facebook • Youtube • Smartphones with apps • ipads • Television • Movies • Video games • Tweeting • MySpace • Pinterest Use/ Consumption of Social Media • 93% of teens are active users of the internet (60-70% daily) • 75% of teens own a cellphone • Teens average over 3000 texts per month (100/day) • Text messaging has increased most dramatically, along with media multi-tasking.

Social media used in various business functions. Some of them are: Marketing- Marketing is one of the most important and common use of social media in business. It works because today every brand has a target section of online audience. HR-Is great for identifying and engaging the talent directly. HR helps company to showcase their employee benefits and culture of the company to outside world. Creative- it share enables art, copy and design teams to invent new ideas which is useful for company to achieve goal. Operations/strategy- Many of the sites like LinkedIn helps the business by connecting with the experts who can share some strategic plans. Business Development- Professional networking sites can be used to connect with the clients.

A historical perspective on social media: Social Media While most benefit is gained from investigating current and future trends of social media, it is important to have an understanding of how social media has developed over the years. Although it started as a rudimentary communication device, it has morphed into a complex and crucial business and social tool representing a multi-billion dollar industry (Sandholm 2011). Several past social media technologies are reviewed below in order to provide an understanding of the foundation for social media and to capture the nature of historical developments in a conceptual framework.

Bulletin board systems Traditionally, bulletin board systems (BBSs) were associated with illegal activity, including playing host to hacking instructions and virus code (Chapman 2009). Bulletin board systems were among the first platforms that allowed users to interact with one another via a personal computer and a telephone modem. Users could log on and access message boards and community file sharing (Border).

6. SOCIAL MEDIA:

A number of niche social media technologies fall into this category, including dating sites, forums, and more "traditional" social networks such as Facebook, Six Degrees, Friendster, MySpace, AsianAvenue, MiGente, Black Planet and Live Journal. These sites were in their infancy at the end of Social Media, but have come into their own in recent years, as they continue to innovate to become more interactive. Many of these sites quickly gained popularity with the masses. The dramatic increase in social networks indicates that users are demanding this kind of connection with others.

Life streaming sites Ustream.tv and Justin.tv are the most well-known life streaming sites. They allow visitors to watch various live videos as well as streaming video feeds, including those from security cameras, traffic cameras, and animal cameras. Most users do not fier constant video steams, but are instead only online occasionally

7. CONCLUSION:

In this paper we have discussed various positive and negative impacts that today media has on society. We find that major chunk of youth is using social media networks more than 5 hours a day resulting in decreasing their general

health in general and mental health in particular. We also found that media is playing both constructive as well as destructive roles on one hand it has lots of advantages but on the other hand it has lots of disadvantages and at the end it "s up to the individual and society to decide which ones to use. .Social media has various merits but it also has some demerits which affect people negatively. False information can lead the education system to failure, in an organization wrong advertisement will affect the productivity, social media can abuse the society by invading on people's privacy, some useless blogs can influence youth that can become violent and can take some inappropriate actions. Use of social media is beneficial but should be used in a limited way without getting addicted.

8. REFERENCES:

- [1] Abhimanyu Shankhdhar, JIMS / Social media and businss
- [2] Mahmoudi Sidi Ahmed et al., "Detection of Abnormal Motions in Multimedia", Chania ICMI-MIAUCE'08 workshop, Crete, Greece, 2008.
- [3] S. Shabnoor, S. Tajinder, Social Media its Impact with Positive and Negative Aspects IJCATR, Volume 5– Issue 2, 71 - 75, 2016
- [4] Bin Zhao et al., "Online Detection of Unusual Events in Multimedia via Dynamic Sparse Coding", 2011.
- [5] Nagar, Himanshu, Chetna Dabas, and J. P. Gupta. "Navie Bayes and K-Means Hybrid Analysis for Extracting Extremist Tweets", ACM Conference, pp 27-32.
- [6] https://www.mckinseyquarterly.com/Capturing_business_value_with_social_technologies_3029 (accessed November 14, 2012)
- [7] <https://www.schooliseasy.com/2014/02/social-media-in-theclassroom/>
- [8] <http://www.edudemic.com/how-students-benefit-from-usingsocialmedia/>
- [9] <http://blog.hootsuite.com/social-media-for-business/>
- [10] <http://www.automatedbuildings.com/news/sep11/columns/110826030404mandrusiak.html>
- [11] http://www.practicalparticipation.co.uk/yes/what/what_does_it_change